

www.arseam.com

MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: NEW AGE HEALTHCARE ENTREPRENEURSHIP – PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES IN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

Nilam Patil , Sruti Mitra, & Anjali Sharma

Assistant Professors ,

Symbiosis Centre for Management studies, Pune,

Symbiosis International University, India

Viman Nagar, Pune - 411014

Abstract

Purpose: *The Purpose of this paper is to put light on the options available in India for Healthcare Entrepreneurship; an emerging trend in form of MEDIPRENEURSHIP and the opportunities and challenges for the medipreneurial ventures in India.*

Background: *Healthcare services in India has a long history of primitive healthcare services starting from around 6th century BC. Continuing this tradition India is seeing a growth in the Healthcare industry today providing wide array of services like Medical tourism; Home based healthcare and Medical Consultation services. The pervasive growth of healthcare entrepreneurship aka MEDIPRENEURSHIP (we are introducing this term for the first time in this paper) has different factors which can serve either as a prospect or as a challenge for these Medipreneurs. This paper aims to converse these factors and its consequence in Indian context.*

Methodology: *This paper is purely based on secondary qualitative data.*

Findings: *The research reveals that with the mounting scope in Healthcare industry one can see spur of Medipreneurs in India. There are few factors like Internet and emergence of information technology and few governmental policies which are creating prospects for medipreneurial ventures; while there are also challenges like unorganized sector, lack of knowledge about this industry and fragmented customer segments and their diverse expectations, which should be tackled by the Medipreneurs to be flourishing in this industry.*

Significance: *The research will significantly contribute to streamline the healthcare sector and to help the Medipreneurs grow in organized manner and also help government policy makers design policies for the growth of Indian Medipreneurs thus boosting the Indian economy.*

**Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship –
Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective**

Keywords: Medipreneurs, Medipreneurship, Medical Tourism, home based healthcare, medical consultancy.

Background:

Since long, India is seen as a world leader in providing medical treatments and surgeries. Medical Science was one area where surprising advances had been made in ancient times in India. Specifically these advances were in the areas of plastic surgery, extraction of cataracts, dental surgery, etc., These are not just tall claims. There is documentary evidence to prove the existence of these practices. In ancient times, it was a tradition to take care of and treat the patients in their own homes and for those who had no one to look after them, the state had arranged places where the patients were lodged and treated.

It is remarkable to note that the states in India all through its history functioned as welfare states and provided well organized health facilities to the destitute and the poor. There are documentary proofs for these services at the times of Cholas, Maurya, Pallava and other dynasties in India. Ayurveda being world’s oldest literature for medicinal practices also originated in India. This is enough to prove that India is a leader in healthcare Services since long and now again it is gaining its position.

India’s healthcare industry (which includes Hospitals, medical Infrastructure, medical devices, Clinical Trials, Outsourcing, Telemedicine, health insurance and Medical Equipments) Is developing at a great pace and is expected to reach \$160 Billion by 2017, according to Frost & Sullivan.

Medipreneur:

The Authors are defining the term for the first time in the context of healthcare entrepreneurship.

According to Authors, “Medipreneur is the Entrepreneur working in healthcare industry as the healthcare Service provider or the Mediator who connects the healthcare service providers with patients or Healthcare Organizations resulting in building an Efficient Healthcare Ecosystem.”

Example of Healthcare service providers can be Doctor, Healthcare experts, and Healthcare organizations etc.

Medipreneurship is the Process of starting a new venture in healthcare and allied services.

Objective:

1. To coin a new term for the growing Healthcare sector in India and entrepreneurial ventures in this sector.
2. To study different types of Medipreneurs in India and the challenges and opportunities for Medipreneurs to grow in Healthcare sector.

Research methodology:

This research paper is principally based on secondary data which has published in various research journals, leading magazine, websites and government reports.

Healthcare Sectors in India:

Authors want to discuss the major sectors for growth of Medipreneurial ventures which include:

1. Medical Tourism
2. Home based Healthcare
3. Medical/ healthcare Consultancy

1. Medical Tourism:

Medical Tourism, sometimes also known as Healthcare tourism or wellness tourism is a growing phenomenon in tourism industry. It is growing rapidly as a niche segment in tourism industry. This term for the first time was coined by Tour operators and media firms but now has become a definition for travel for Healthcare Services in different locations.

Medical tourism is the travel for all kinds of medical facilities and healthcare available in some other countries. Sometimes the travel is within country but generally this term extends to the medical facilities sought outside the patient's home country and across international borders. Earlier the flow was from developing countries to the industrialized nations for better and technologically advanced medical facilities, but now a day the picture is quite different where one can see the growth of these types of services and service providers in third world nations.(M. Horowitz, J. Rosenweig; 2008).

**Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship –
Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective**

According to industry estimates, around seven million patients are said to be travelling each year to receive medical care. Due to the highly fragmented nature of the industry and different definitions, there are various estimates of the market size. The global medical tourism industry was estimated at USD 10.5 billion in 2012. It is expected to grow at a CAGR of 17.9 per cent from 2013-19 to reach USD 32.5 billion in 2019. (KPMG report)

The Opportunities in the Indian Medical Tourism market are created due to Global demand for Low-cost and High quality, sophisticated medical treatments. Patients from the neighboring countries like the Middle East, Africa, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Myanmar and also from other countries like Commonwealth of Independent states (CIS), Australia, US and Canada, and few European countries travel to India to avail medical facilities.

“The vast pool of medical professionals, expanding private health-care infrastructure, growing technical expertise, cheaper medical procedures, world class health-care infrastructure and government support are likely to boost the number of medical tourists arrivals in India to a projected level of 0.4 Million by 2018,” said Sharad Jaipuria, president, PHD Chamber.

India hosts about 150,000 medical tourists annually, and this number is expected to grow by 15 per cent every year. (Accenture report, *India in 2014*)

Strengths of Indian Medical Tourism sector:

1. Low Cost High Quality Treatments
2. The geographical location of India for better connectivity with global patients
3. Availability of Internationally trained and expert and experienced Medical Staff
4. Lesser language barriers due to more number of English Speaking people
5. Sustained Reputation for Clinical excellence
6. History of Healthcare innovation and Achievement
7. State-of-the-art medical technology and infrastructure
8. Indian Hospitals with International Accreditations to build confidence and trust of travelers.
9. Lesser waiting time for treatments and timely guidance by Doctors
10. Alternative medical Treatments available e.g.: Ayurveda and Yoga

India's JCI-accredited hospitals now number 21, up from only two in 2005.

Standards and Accreditation: Joint Commission International (JCI)

Hospitals and Clinics with JCI accreditation:

- Fortis Escorts Heart Institute
- Fortis Hospital Bangalore& Mumbai
- Shroff Eye Hospital and LASIK Center
- Rotunda: The Center for Human Reproduction
- Max Healthcare and Super-Specialty Hospitals
- Apollo Hospitals Group
- Columbia Asia India
- Dr. L H Hiranandani Hospital
- Narayana Hridayalaya

The following table explains the costs of general procedures in India and US:

	Procedure Cost (US\$) (2010)	
	United States	India
Bone Marrow Transplant	2,50,000	69,000
Liver Transplant	3,00,000	69,000
Heart Surgery	30,000	8,000
Orthopedic Surgery	20,000	6,000
Cataract Surgery	2,000	1,250

Source: www.patientsbeyondborders.com

The top specialties sought out by medical travelers in India:

- Cosmetic surgery

Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship – Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective

- Dentistry (general, restorative, cosmetic)
- Cardiovascular (angioplasty, CABG, transplants)
- Orthopedics (joint and spine; sports medicine)
- Cancer (often high-acuity or last resort)
- Reproductive (fertility, IVF, women's health)
- Weight loss (LAP-BAND, gastric bypass)
- Scans, tests, health screenings and second opinions.

Challenges of Indian Medical Tourism sector:

1. Unorganized sector: No Coordination among the various service providers in the industry– airline, hotels, travel agents and hospitals
2. Lesser Infrastructural and technological developments as compared to the Developed countries.
3. Flow of medical expert from India to other countries.
4. Less number of Doctors: India faces an enormous shortage of hospital beds with just 0.9 beds for every 1000 population (WHO) as against a world average of 3.96 beds per 1000 population (Technopak)
5. Growing Competition from other countries in the medical tourism sector.
6. Low-investment in health infrastructure
7. Unhygienic country as per Perception of the Customer
8. No mandatory accreditation and regulation system for hospitals
9. The cultural barriers for foreign patients/Travelers.

Prospects for Indian Medical Tourism sector:

1. Government’s Initiatives like Private Public Partnership (PPP), Visa on Arrival and increased spending in healthcare sector will work as a boost for the sector.

2. India's official national health policy encourages medical travel as part of its economy's "export" activities, although the services are performed within India
3. Insurance policies in other countries which don't provide assistance in few services like orthopedic surgeries, cosmetic surgeries etc.
4. Reduced air-fares and Travel expenses.
5. The success rate in surgeries especially Heart surgeries and orthopedic replacement surgeries.
6. Increased demand for healthcare services from countries like US, UK with aging population.
7. Changing insurance policies in different countries.

2. Home Based Health Care

It is a medical care that brings doctors and hospitals right at one's doorstep over a single phone call. In India, it is rapidly emerging as an important field and is undergoing a transformation. Once an unorganized and fragmented sector, it is becoming an organized, technology-led industry with standards and protocols. Startups and investors are shifting from the traditional delivery system platform to these disruptive technologies to pioneer a medical care model to address healthcare needs at the comfort of homes.

Opportunities:

The home health care delivery system is an "important but underdeveloped component" of the larger health care delivery system in India. (Mukherjee of IIMB).

The concept is gradually catching up in India. A recent paper by consulting firm Pacific Bridge Medical notes that the global home health care market, which includes devices, products and services, was worth almost \$215 billion in 2013 and is projected to grow at 8% per annum until 2020.

**Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship –
Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective**

In US, it is an established model pegged around \$80 billion. Pacific Bridge Medical estimates the Indian home health care market, still at nascent stage around \$3 billion and growing rapidly at the rate of more than 18%.

The potential for this business is huge and is becoming imperative for the following reasons:

1. Life expectancy increasing significantly in India-India has the second largest geriatric (ageing) population in the world. The concept of old-age homes is socially largely unacceptable in India and therefore better home-based health care facilities are becoming mandatory. It is estimated that for an average individual, 70% of health care needs can be met in the home environment. Globally, geriatric care accounts for 70 % of home healthcare visits (TOI, 8th June 2014).
2. According to a United Nations Population Fund report, the number of people aged 60 and over in India will increase from 100 million in 2011 to 300 million by 2050;
3. The growth of NRIs, nuclear families and those who work from home (TOI, 8th June)
4. Changing disease patterns with the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases.
5. Need for better quality post-operative and primary care due to abysmal doctor-patient ratio and low hospital bed density in the country
6. Sizable population in India that needs and is willing to pay for these services. This makes it a viable business proposition for entrepreneurs and their investors. As this market grows, the profit streams can be huge and long-term, and lead to large returns on capital invested.
7. Even Basic healthcare is not accessible to population in remote towns and villages in India.

8. Advances in communication and medical technology - results in interventions and medical gadgets with which most of the patient monitoring for diseases like heart failure , respiratory failure, Alzheimer's which was previously possible only in hospitals, can now be offered with remarkable ease at home environment. (Notes Dr. Devi Prasad Shetty, a cardiac surgeon based in Bangalore and founder of the Narayana Health Group)

Benefits:

- To the hospital systems - they can reduce costs and become more efficient by reducing the average length of stay and [enabling] quicker turnover of patients.(Arockiasamy of IHHC)
- To the patients – helps decrease the direct and indirect medical costs of patients to a large extent in the following ways:
 - With better home management of chronic care, the patient is able to come to the hospital at an early stage of the disease and receive less intensive and sometimes even less invasive care.
 - Patients gain from better health outcomes because they are not exposed to hospital – borne infections

Table: Exhibits the various types of home healthcare service, target segments and service providers.

Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship – Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective

Healthcare Service	Basic Healthcare	Chronic diseases & Specialty services	Post - Operative	Allied Services
Subtypes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>geriatric care (elder care)</i> • <i>palliative care</i> • <i>primary care</i> • <i>physiotherapy</i> • collection of lab samples • home delivery of medicines • orthopedic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • heart failure • COPD • chronic arthritis • cancer care • chronic diabetes • neurological health • Medical equipment for hire. or personalized wearable • Rehabilitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post operative surgical site management • ICU Care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yoga • Ayurveda treatment
Demographic Target Segment	Ageing population 45-80 age group	Ageing population	Any age group	Any age group
Service provider	Doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, caregivers, office staff	Doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, caregivers, office staff	Doctors, nurses, physiotherapists	Ayurveda Doctors, Yoga trainers

Source: Prepared by Author based on different sources.

Revenue Stream: Most service providers have a revenue stream comprising one or more of the following with the charges varying across geographies and severity of the disease.

- Long term care package
- Annual care plan (ranging from Rs. 12,000 to 15,000)
- Monthly subscription fees
- Single everyday service
- ICU Setting: at home ranges from Rs. 7500 a day – 50 percent cost effective from corporate hospitals.
- NRI Package : Non-resident Indians (NRIs) can sign up for customized in-home health care services for their relatives in India and get regular updates from the company.

Types of Service Providers :

- **Large hospital chains** - like the Manipal Group and Max Healthcare have also started providing this service either on their own or through partnerships with standalone providers.
- **Specialized Home Healthcare companies**
 - Portea Medical, a Bangalore-based home health care firm-Meena and K. Ganesh for basic Healthcare needs.
 - Medwell Ventures, a “specialty” home health care company
 - Healthcare at Home, which is backed by the Burman family of the Dabur Group
 - Bayada, one of the largest private home health firms in the U.S., took a 26% stake in India Home Health Care (IHHC) a Chennai-based
 - Homital Medcare
 - CauseforSmile – meeting the needs of the NRIs concerning parents’ fitness, health, recreation as well as social aspects.

Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship – Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective

- Government-run primary health care centers
- Private family physicians

Challenges faced in delivering health care at home :

1. Consistency in quality and continuum of care for the patients- Home healthcare particularly cancer care requires “strong management, medical oversight, and high-quality chemotherapy nurses supported by a quality controlled pharmacy. We need clear, evidence-based treatment protocols that cover the range of protocols delivered by the team.” (David Kerr, Professor of cancer medicine at the University of Oxford)

2. Lack of skilled manpower: One of the biggest drawbacks in expanding home health care system in India is the lack of a structured educational and other vocational training program for Para-medical and other home health services (Shetty of Narayana Health).

3. Health Insurance Policies: Home health care in India is not covered by most health Insurance policies. In future, organized players will bring in credibility, standards and accountability which could encourage insurance companies to cover home health care giving a further boost to this sector (PwC’s Mehta).

4. Right Business Model: Home health care is believed to be a low margin business. It is a volume game so scalability is important for its profitability. Technology and Execution capabilities are critical for its success. Ability to handle the logistics to manage other remote workers, scheduling appointments, continuous monitoring for personalized treatment, analyzing patient data will play a crucial role in their success. As the business model and core competencies of specialized players are different from that of large hospitals, the former are believed to be more effective in service delivery than the latter.(Medwell’s Bali and Portea’s Ganesh)In contrast to the previous view, big hospitals equipped with strong infrastructure, trained manpower and expanded network of referrals can provide better service (Shetty). So the viable business model can be the coexistence of the standalone home healthcare companies with the large hospitals by tie-up. (Balachandran)

Thus discovering the right business model , market segment , technology and the quality of care will play a vital role for this home based healthcare business to be successful (Ajit Mahadevan , leader Life Sciences , Ernst & Young – (Monday 8th June , Times of India)

3. Medical/ healthcare Consultancy

Online Medical consultancies are the IT enabled services provided by healthcare service providers for patients and medical/healthcare (physicians) organizations. These generally work as an intermediary between two counterparts i.e. Two organizations or between organization and patients.

These have different types based on the services provided:

- I. Telemedicine.
- II. Healthcare consultancy/database services.
- III. Medical Transcription services.

I. Telemedicine

Consultancy and treatment when provided with the help of IT, satellite and fiber optic network is Telemedicine.

Medical consultancy in India is in the midst of a major market transition and technology is making tremendous impact in the way healthcare is delivered. These are generally used by service providers from different countries to make use of state of the art technology and of experts to diagnose the disease and to provide better cure at a distance. Telemedicine is required to eliminate the distance related barriers by connecting remote locations and improving the access to medical services for people across countries and for the rural areas where the access has always been a problem.

Telemedicine is often misunderstood as a synonym of telehealth and e-health. But it is altogether different terminology due to the reason that it refers to all clinical services, whereas telehealth

**Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship –
Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective**

takes care of clinical and non-clinical services along with medical education, administration and research.

Definition

There are several definitions of telemedicine. According to World Health Organization, telemedicine is defined as, *“The delivery of healthcare services, where distance is a critical factor, by all healthcare professionals using information and communication technologies for the exchange of valid information for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and for continuing education of healthcare providers, all in the interests of advancing the health of individuals and their communities”*.

Three categories of Telemedicine are:

- Real-time or interactive services: where through telephonic or online communication patients can directly contact service providers. Based on historical review and psychiatric evaluation the assessment can be done.
- Remote monitoring: This is the method used to monitor patient indirectly using various technologies, it was used earlier for chronic diseases only but gives comparable results in cost effective manner.
- Store and forward telemedicine: Technique through which medical images are first acquired and then on the availability of medical specialists the properly structured medical record is shared. The assessment is done based on these medical records, history of patients and audio/video report of the physical examination. (CCI 2013)

It is generally done through satellite communication and ITES.

These services include, Telecardiology, Telecardiology and Tele-imaging.

➤ **Telecardiology**

Telecardiology, a branch of telemedicine, which helps patients through teleconsultation, by enabling cardiovascular treatment from a distant place, either from home or in different part of

world. It helps cardiologists across the world to get connected and give consultations. Both cardiac patients and healthcare Professionals can benefit from telecardiology.

➤ **Teleradiology**

Teleradiology is the most established and most widely used term of the umbrella term called Telemedicine, through which specialist/radiologist opinion is obtained by sending images on internet and other channels.

This requires the use of satellite, internet, mobile phones and computer systems works with three major components called an image sending station, transmission network and a review station.

➤ **Tele-imaging:**

Tele-imaging is an important part of telemedicine as it is an area which comes under Teleradiology and includes the transmission of medical digital images and plays a role in all fields of telemedicine, such as expertise, consultation, teaching and research. (Bonnin A., 1999)

II. MEDICAL TRANSCRIPTION:

Medical transcription is the practice of typing (transcribing) the medical records dictated audio files by doctors or healthcare experts.

MT is an IT enabled service (ITES), which comprises medical notes dictated by a physician in the form of editable electronic documents to be added to patient records (Ghodeswar and Vaidyanathan, 2008).

As it is made compulsory by the insurance providers; in most of the foreign countries; to have the written/typed medical records of patients, the need of Medical transcription service is growing faster. These services are outsourced from Developed countries to developing countries because of cost advantage due to cheap labor and currency rates in developing countries.

The global medical transcription services market was valued at USD 41.4 million in 2012 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 5.6% from 2013 to 2019, to reach an estimated value of USD 60.6 million in 2019. (PRNewswire)

Indian Medipreneurs have an opportunity and a competitive edge over others because of following factors:

- The availability of educated and skilled workforce.
- The state of the art technology and infrastructure available
- IT and ITES service availability
- Lesser communication barriers.
- Time difference with different countries.

Challenges in Medical Transcription sector:

- The patient’s privacy issue due to shared information
- The quality of the transcription services which is based on the education level language barriers of the medical transcriptionist.

Factors responsible for Growth of Online consultancy:

- Bridging gap between isolated communities of patients and healthcare providers.
- Teaching and Information sharing tool
- Cost effectiveness.
- Time saving.
- Expert advice can be sought by healthcare professionals and patients in remote areas.

III. Healthcare consultancy /database services

Advent of digitization in the healthcare industry necessitated the transformation from paper to electronic records by collection of data organized for storage, accessibility and retrieval is called healthcare database. Most acknowledged data in the healthcare is online transaction processing (OLTP) database which gives the wide range of transactional applications such as:

- Practice management system
- EHR: Electronic Health Record
- Costing system
- Patient satisfaction
- Radiology
- Pathology

Online medical/healthcare services are a growing market in India due to strengths of service providers. Following are the reasons for growth of these online consultancies and potential areas of thrust for the Medipreneurs in this area.

Strengths of Indian Medipreneurs in Healthcare Consultancies:

- ITES services
- Reduced language barriers
- Availability of skill
- Human Resource
- Infrastructure availability
- State of the art technology
- Government support.
- Elimination of distance barriers.

Challenges for Healthcare Consultancies:

- More government initiative.
- Unorganized sector.
- Speed of network
- Quality infrastructure.
- Liability and Ethical aspects.
- Patients' mind set.

Prospects for Growth in Healthcare Consultancy sector:

- Increasing consumer base
- Cost effective technology
- Working population
- More productive and less time consuming

**Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship –
Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective**

Conclusion:

The research reveals that with the mounting scope in Healthcare industry one can see spur of Medipreneurs in India. The increasing opportunities in this sector are due to the fact that the sector is at nascent state.

Many factors related to Indian Healthcare service providers, Infrastructural and technological developments, Government policy changes and India’s geographical location provide a prospect for Indian Medipreneurs to grow in different streams of healthcare services. There are few factors like Internet and emergence of information technology and few governmental policies which are creating major prospects for medipreneurial ventures.

While the picture is not all rosy and there are challenges like unorganized sector, lack of knowledge about this industry and fragmented customer segments and their diverse expectations, which should be tackled by the Medipreneurs to be flourishing in this industry.

To make the sector well organized and for growth of Medipreneurs in India government should make interventions through making policies to support entrepreneurs in healthcare sector. In addition to this all the Healthcare service providers, Healthcare organizations, and mediators should work in concert to build an efficient healthcare ecosystem which will help to boost current and budding Medipreneurs.

References:

- Bonnin A., 1999. [Medical tele-imaging: a good chance for the future](#). *Bull AcadNatl Med.* 1999;183(6):1123-34
- Ghodeswar, B., Vaidyanathan, J. (2008), "Business process outsourcing: an approach to gain access to world-class capabilities", *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol. 14 No.1, pp.23-38.
- Mahesh Uniyal et.al. February 2014. SWOT Analysis of Indian medical Tourism Industry: *Paripex - Indian Journal Of Research Vol. 3/2*
- Michael d. Horowitz and Jeffrey E. Rosensweig. February 2008. Medical Tourism Vs Traditional International Medical Travel: A Tale of two Models. *International Medical Travel Journal*
- NishigandhaBurute and BhavinJankharia, February 2009. Teleradiology: The Indian perspective. *Indian Journal of Radiology and Imaging.*19 (1): 16–18.
- Suman Kumar dawn, Swati pal. July 2011. “Medical Tourism in India: Issues, Opportunities and Designing Strategies for Growth and Development”.*International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Vol.1/3*
- V.Mahesh, A.Kandaswamy, and R.Venkatesan (November 2009), “Telecardiology for Rural Health Care”, *International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering*, Vol. 2, No. 3
- Brief report on healthcare, telemedicine & medical tourism in India, October 2013, *corporate catalyst India (CCI)*
- Data Warehouse Article by Drew Cardon. Understanding the Healthcare Database: Purposes, Strengths, and Weaknesses. <https://www.healthcatalyst.com/healthcare-database-purposes-strengths-weaknesses>
- Deloitte/global/Life-Sciences-Health-Care/dttl-lshc-2014-global-health-care-sector-report.pdf
- IBEF, December 2013 <http://www.ibef.org/industry/healthcare-india.aspx>
- Health Care in India (2002): The Road Ahead , CII, McKinsey and Company

Nilam , Sruti, & Anjali/ MEDIPRENEURSHIP”: New Age Healthcare Entrepreneurship – Prospects and Challenges in Indian Perspective

KPMG in India analysis, 2014.
<http://www.kpmg.com/IN/en/IssuesAndInsights/ArticlesPublications/Documents/KPMG-FICCI-Heal-Sep2014.pdf>

McKinsey report on The emerging market in health care innovation by Tilman Ehrbeck, Nicolaus Henke, and Thomas Kibasi , **May 2010**

McKinsey report on Spurring the market for high-tech home health care by Basel Kayyali, Zeb Kimmel, and Steve van Kuiken ,**September 2011**

Medical Transcription Services Market, 2013. - Global Industry Analysis, Size, Share, Growth, Trends and Forecast, 2013 - 2019". <http://www.prnewswire.com/>.

Model/Home Health Care in India: In Search of the Right Business Model Sep 11, 2014:
<http://knowledge.wharton.upenn.edu/article/home-health-care-india-search-right-business>
<http://www.patientsbeyondborders.com/medical-tourism-statistics-facts>

Home healthcare is an emerging field in India, experts say, Sep 25, 2014, The Times of India:
<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/Home-healthcare-is-an-emerging-field-in-India-experts-say/articleshow/43449000.cms>

‘International medical tourism industry pegged at USD 40 billion a year’, Economic Times,27 June 2013

‘Medical tourism hamstrung by obsolete visa rules’, BusinessStandard, 2 December 2013

<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/ Startups bring doc and hospital home, June 8th 2014>